

First country records of *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERMAR, 1824) (Coleoptera: Erotylidae) from Albania and Montenegro

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JERZY BOROWSKI¹ , ŁUKASZ MINKINA²,
SEBASTIAN TYLKOWSKI³

¹ Department of Forest Protection, Institute of Forest Sciences, Warsaw University of Life Sciences – SGGW, Nowoursynowska 159/34, 02-776 Warsaw, Poland, e-mail: jerzy_borowski@sggw.edu.pl, ORCID: 0000-0002-7678-5364; tomasz_gazurek@sggw.edu.pl, ORCID: 0000-0002-3143-3285; adam_byk@sggw.edu.pl, ORCID: 0000-0001-9505-3436

² 34-400 Nowy Targ, Poland, e-mail: klekel@interia.eu

³ Department of Forest Research, University of Lodz, Branch in Tomaszów Mazowiecki, Konstytucji 3 Maja 65, 97-200 Tomaszów Mazowiecki, Poland, e-mail: sebastian.tylkowski@uni.lodz.pl, ORCID: 0000-0002-0423-2963

ABSTRACT. First country records of *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERMAR, 1824) (Coleoptera: Erotylidae) from Albania and Montenegro.

The paper provides information about a rarely reported beetle of the family Erotylidae, for the first time found in Albania and Montenegro. The beetle is *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERMAR, 1824), which was caught in three sites in northern Albania and south-eastern part of Montenegro.

KEY WORDS: pleasing fungus beetles, Encaustini, new locality, faunistic data, Balkans.

The genus *Aulacochilus* CHEVROLAT, 1837 belongs to the tribe Encaustini, subfamily Erotylinae and family Erotylidae. There are 19 species in the Palaearctic Region, 17 of which inhabit Asia (8 of which were introduced to the Oriental region), one - North Africa and one lives in Europe – *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERMAR, 1824) (WĘGRZYNOWICZ 2007). The last mentioned was described from Sicily (GERMAR 1824), and now, besides Italy, it is only known from four countries, namely: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Romania (HELLER 1920, WĘGRZYNOWICZ 2007) and Turkey (GBIF 2025). Thanks to its metallic blue body colour *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) is a very characteristic species, easy to recognise (Fig. 1). However, due to its cryptic lifestyle, it is very rarely collected.

Below is new data about the distribution of *A. violaceus* in the Balkans. At the same time, these are first reports of this species in Albania and Montenegro (Fig. 2).

Albania: Gropat e Selcës at Lëpushë, 42°32'17"N 19°40'52"E, 1 430 m a.s.l., 6 VI 2016, 21 exx., under the bark of a rotten and fungus-covered tree trunk, leg. et coll. T. Gazurek (Fig. 3).

Montenegro: Žanjev Do at Njeguši, 42°25'08"N 18°48'36"E, 1 120 m a.s.l., 25 V 2021, 14 exx., on fruiting bodies of *Cerioporus squamosus* (HUDS.) QUÉLET growing on a tree stump, leg. A. Byk, coll. T. Gazurek; Dubovik at Cetynia, 42°24'40"N 18°53'08"E, 920 m a.s.l., 26 V 2021, 3 exx., in a moldy forest litter, leg. et coll. T. Gazurek (Figs 4–5).

Fig. 1. *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.), dorsal view (photo Ł. Minkina).

Ryc. 1. *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.), widok z góry (fot. Ł. Minkina).

The above beetle species, like most Erotylidae representatives closely related to it, is a typical mycetophile, trophically connected with fruiting bodies of Polyporales. It is nocturnal, during the day imagines hide in the inhabited fruiting bodies of fungi, wood cracks, under protruding bark or in forest floor cover, but always near their feeding material. In Montenegro numerous specimens of the beetles in question were collected from a fruiting body of *Cerioporus squamosus* (HUDS.) QUÉLET, which seems to be a host species for *A. violaceus*.

Aulacochilus violaceus (GERM.) was placed on the Red List of Mediterranean Saproxyllic Beetles (GARCIA *et al.* 2008), category DD (data deficient species).

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Fig. 2. Collection localities of *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) in Albania (1 – Gropat e Selcës ad Lëpushë) and Montenegro (2 – Žanjev Do ad Njeguši, 3 – Dubovik ad Cetynia).

Ryc. 2. Miejsca odłowu *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) w Albanii (1 – Gropat e Selcës ad Lëpushë) i Czarnogórze (2 – Žanjev Do ad Njeguši, 3 – Dubovik ad Cetynia).

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Fig. 3. A sampling site of *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) in Albania – Gropat e Selcës ad Lëpushë (photo T. Gazurek).

Ryc. 3. Przykładowe stanowisko *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) w Albanii – Gropat e Selcës ad Lëpushë (fot. T. Gazurek).

Fig. 4. A sampling site of *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) in Montenegro – Žanjev Do ad Njeguši (photo S. Tylkowski).

Ryc. 4. Przykładowe stanowisko *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) w Czarnogórze – Žanjev Do ad Njeguši (fot. S. Tylkowski).

Fig. 5. A sampling site of *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) in Montenegro – Dubovik ad Cetynia (photo A. Byk).
Ryc. 5. Przykładowe stanowisko *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERM.) w Czarnogórze – Dubovik ad Cetynia (fot. A. Byk).

Streszczenie

Pierwsze krajowe dane dotyczące *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERMAR, 1824) (Coleoptera: Erotylidae) z Albanii i Czarnogóry

Artykuł przedstawia informacje o rzadko wykazywanym chrząszczu z rodziny Erotylidae, po raz pierwszy znalezionym w Albanii i Czarnogórze. Chrząszczem tym jest *Aulacochilus violaceus* (GERMAR, 1824), który został złapany w trzech miejscach w północnej Albanii i południowo-wschodniej części Czarnogóry.

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